

BLAZE: Appendix

May 2023

A.1 Dataset Statistics

Table 1: Statistics of the train split of BeetleBox.

Project	# Bugs	Avg. buggy file
ClickHouse	1,993	3.77
posthog	468	3.2
airflow	1,945	2.89
dolphinscheduler	1,577	2.95
axios	191	2.7
dagger	501	3.06
elasticsearch	1,792	2.79
godot	1,875	2.1
localstack	639	3.26
act	257	2.67
odoo	161	1.66
pytorch	2	2.0
next.js	1,783	3.7

A.1.1 Dataset Quality

We assessed the dataset’s quality across three dimensions. First, we measured the lengths of report titles and descriptions, as longer titles and descriptions often reflect more comprehensive information. Second, we evaluated the bug report quality score using the methodology proposed by Bettenburg et al.[1]. Table3 presents the dataset’s statistical details.

Table 2: Statistics of the test split of BeetleBox.

Project	# Bugs	Avg. buggy file
OpenRefine	878	2.4
selenium	280	2.48
ansible	1434	3.06
dubbo	633	1.96
bitcoin	931	2.53
ccxt	790	1.4
cryptomator	99	3.76
electron	3480	2.8
react	626	2.98
fastify	400	3.06
guava	26	4.88
langchain	220	2.03
liquibase	354	2.62
pdf.js	788	3.46
nats-server	400	3.03
onnx	155	3.08
protobuf	372	2.59
svelte	1271	4.13

Table 3: Dataset statistics regarding quality.

Attribute	50 percentile	90 percentile
Report Title Length	58	91
Report Description Length	1,148	4,954
Quality Score	35	55

A.2 Hyperparameter set

Code 1: Hyper-parameters for fine-tuning

```

1 {
2   "padding": "max_length",
3   "device": "cuda:0",

```

```
4   "epochs": 15,  
5   "batch_size": 80,  
6   "scheduler": "WarmupLinear",  
7   "warmup_steps": 100,  
8   "optimizer_class": "AdamW",  
9   "optimizer_params": {  
10      "lr": 2e-7,  
11  }  
12   "weight_decay": 0.01,  
13   "max_grad_norm": 1  
14 }
```

A.3 Dynamic Chunking Simulation

A.3.1 Illustration of of limited context window issues

Table 4: Chunk vs complete file similarity comparison.

Content	Cosine Similarity
Chunk1	0.12
Chunk2	0.08
Full Source Code File	0.15

Prior studies have shown that breaking large text into smaller chunks often leads to poorer-quality embeddings. This is because chunking disrupts the semantic coherence and inter-sentential dependencies within the text, causing embeddings to miss key contextual details. For bug localization tasks, this loss of context can lead to reduced similarity scores between bug reports and relevant code, resulting in false positives or negatives. For example, consider a bug report stating:

The app crashes when trying to load user profiles with missing data. The error seems related to a NullPointerException in the UserProfileManager class.

Code 2: Hyper-parameters for fine-tuning

```
1 public class UserProfileManager {
2     public void loadProfile(User user) {
3         if (user == null || user.getData() == null) {
4             throw new NullPointerException("User profile data is
5                 ↪ missing");
6         }
7         // Additional profile loading logic
8     }
9     //-----Break Point-----
10    public void displayProfile(User user) {
11        if (user.getData() == null) {
12            System.out.println("Error: Profile data is missing");
13        } else {
14            System.out.println("Displaying profile for " +
15                ↪ user.getName());
16        }
17    }
18 }
```

and the corresponding buggy source code file is illustrated in Code 2. Suppose we divide the code into two chunks using a fixed window approach. Then, we

calculate the similarity between each chunk and the bug report, as well as the similarity between the full source code and the bug report. This result is shown in Table 4. As shown, the similarity score for the full source code is higher (0.15) than for either of the chunks individually. This occurs because the model processes the entire context, generating an embedding that represents the complete functionality of the source file. In contrast, each chunk lacks information from other chunks (e.g., chunk 2 cannot reference context in chunk 1), leading to lower-quality embeddings. In scenarios with multiple source files, this can cause low similarity scores for buggy files and lead to incorrect predictions. Therefore, a limited context window is a challenge for effective bug localization.

A.3.2 Simulation of Dynamic Chunking

We address this problem through dynamic chunking, which preserves semantic boundaries in code. Specifically, we chunk source code files at logical boundaries like methods, classes, or interfaces to retain as much contextual information as possible. Using the example above, we first identify the positions of code components and their boundaries, which in this case are:

- **Class boundary:** lines 1 to 13
- **Method boundaries:** lines 2 to 6 and lines 7 to 14.

Dynamic chunking works by calculating the cost of breaking the code at each boundary. We populate a dynamic programming (DP) array that stores the cumulative cost up to each line (illustrated in Table 5, and then we identify breakpoints by tracing back through the DP array to find optimal split points. This method leads to chunks aligned with semantic boundaries. For this example, optimal breakpoints would be at lines 1 to 6 and lines 7 to 10. This chunking approach helps ensure that each chunk retains meaningful, complete context, enhancing the embedding quality and reducing the risk of false positives or negatives during bug localization.

Table 5: Cost of chunking up to each line.

Line No.	Cost upto line
0	-1
1	13
2	20
3	20
4	20
5	20
6	20
7	30
8	30
9	30
10	30
11	30
12	30
13	30
14	30

References

- [1] N. Bettenburg, S. Just, A. Schröter, C. Weiss, R. Premraj, and T. Zimmermann, “What makes a good bug report?” in *Proceedings of the 16th ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of software engineering*. ACM, Nov. 2008.